

WAYS OF EXPRESSING THE NATIONAL MENTALITY IN TRANSLATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6473699>

Ataniyazova Nargiza Jalgasbaevna

The master of Karakalpak State University

The department of comparative linguistics and linguistic translation

Annotation: *This article examines the problems of national re-creation in the translation of a work of art and provides additional insights. Problems arising in the process of translating samples of Uzbek literature into English, Russian and other languages were discussed. Theoretical information on the reconstruction of history and nationality is provided. National words are an integral part of the language of the work, through which the author creates the image of the hero, helps to accurately and accurately describe the national identity of the people.*

Keywords: *National color, history, nationality, literary translation, specific words.*

INTRODUCTION

Nationality consists of the peculiarities of the spiritual activity and material life of a nation. Spiritual activity can include people's character, way of thinking, psyche, aspirations, actions, humor, and so on. Material life includes customs, rituals, ceremonies, clothing, household utensils, musical instruments, cooking, names, and so on. This set of national features reflected in works of art is called national color in literature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Restoring the national form of a work of art is one of the important problems of literary translation. There is a great deal of experience in conveying national identity through other languages. However, the principles and criteria of this field are not fully developed. Basic research and studies are ongoing. The problem of re-creating nationalism in the translation of works of art only becomes apparent when the work is compared to another language. A reader who is fluent in Russian will, of course, be able to read a work of art in its original language. If his favorite work is translated into his native language, he will definitely read it in his native language. A bilingual work of art may complain that the reader has not received either praise or original impressions. Therefore, in order for translation to be more than just an experience, a translator must be left-handed, resourceful, and critical of himself.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Translation is also a phenomenon of art, the art of reproduction. If ten people translate a work of art, their translations will not be exactly the same as if they came from the same pattern, but will be significantly different. Because every translator is a

creator. But they are not the same. Each aims to reflect the style of the author. "Every time, a translator and two alpinists come to the translation site one by one." [2, 18] A translator is also a creator, no matter how much he loves the author's style, no matter how much he forces himself to obey the author's will, the unique style of each translator is felt.

As you know, any translation is creative to some extent. The translation of works of art is an art climate in that it requires a special approach and requires skill and artistry. Gaybulla Salomov, head of the Uzbek translation studies department, says:

"The essence of the translation process is to find alternative means of language to preserve the unity and integrity of the form and the content reflected in the original." [3, 149]

Literary translation has many requirements, large and small, such as re-creating the author's style, maintaining the rhythm and intonation of the work, reflecting the speech of the characters with their naturalness, giving national color, finding alternative variants of phraseology, expressing dialectal features. So, they would only resort to this as a last resort.

Creating an imaginative translation of a work of art written in another language at the level of the requirements of the time makes it necessary for the artist to be well-equipped with practical and theoretical knowledge in this field. Because the penman, who has mastered the secrets of artistic mastery in all respects, as a talented person who has embodied the art of expressing the idea in a genuine way, is able to create a full-fledged artistic translation. possible.

Although there are sometimes semantic units in the language of translation that are somewhat closer to the meanings of the original concepts of life, they differ from their conditional equivalents, so this difference does not allow them to be interchanged in translation. For example, the transliteration of words that mean many things, such as money and distance-length units, household items, clothing, food and drink, belonging to the people of origin, is reflected in the play. It provides a vivid picture of the unique environment and conditions in the eyes of the reader.

Below, we have analyzed the translation of common titles, professional words, and realities (national words) in the historical-archaic concepts that define historicity in the novel *The Last Days*. It is important that this is fully reflected in the translation.

Origin: "Musulmonqul Normuhammad qushbegiga besh ming sipoh qo'shib, Toshkand ustiga jo'natqan!" [5, 33]

Uzbek to English translation: "Musulmonqul sent troops of five thousand people to Normuhammad Qushbegi to lead a riot against Tashkent!" [6, 35]

Uzbek to Russian translation: "Мусулманкул отправил в Ташкент пять тысяч воинов, во главе которых стоит Нармухаммад кушбеги"

*Кушбеги – почетное звание правителя города или области. [7]

Russian to English translation: Musulmon Kul has sent five thousand warriors headed by Nar Mohammed Kushbegi* to suppress the uprising!”

*Kushbegi- title of the first minister of the khan’s court. [6, 37]

CONCLUSION

The language of translation with the original is not directly equal to each other. The linguistic possibilities of both languages are not "equivalent" to each other. Therefore, it is not possible to translate blindly. The exact meaning and aesthetic qualities of the words are not mutually exclusive. Therefore, the more fluent the language of the text, the more difficult it is to translate from the artistic point of view.” In these cases, there is a discrepancy between the original and the translation.

REFERENCES:

1. Hotamov N., Sarimsokov B. Russian-Uzbek Glossary of Literary Terms [Russian-Uzbek Glossary of Literary Terms]. - Tashkent, 1983.
2. Hamroyev H. National words - realities and literary translation // Translation culture (Collection of articles) [National words - realities and fiction translation // Culture of translation (Collection of articles)]. - Tashkent, 1982.
3. Salomov G ?. Introduction to translation theory. Tashkent: Teacher, 1978.
4. Quronov D. Theoretical notes [Theoretical notes]. Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2018.
5. Abdullah Qadiri. Last days. Sharq Publishing House / Tashkent.
6. Abdullah Qadiri. The Days Gone by. Novel. Translators: I.M. Tukhtasinov, O.M.Muminov, A.A.Khamidov. Tashkent: “MASHHUR-PRESS”, 2017.
7. Abdulla Kadyri. Minuvshiye dni. Roman, Tashkent.